

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project work entitled “FACTORS AFFECTING THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE” submitted to the Cardiff Metropolitan University, is a record of an original work done by me under the guidance of Ms. Gunathma Gunawardena, and this project work is submitted in the partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of Master of Business Administration. The results embodied in this thesis have not been submitted to any other University or Institute for the award of any degree or diploma.

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ABSTRACT

Although finance has been studied for thousand years, behavioral finance which considers the human behaviors in finance is a quite new area. Behavioral finance theories, which are based on the psychology, attempt to understand how emotions and cognitive errors impact high networth individual investors' decision making.

The main objective of this study is identifying the behavioral factors that have an impact in decision making of high networth individual investors' in the Colombo Stock Exchange. As this is a first attempt on behavioral finance with High Networth Individual Investors in Sri Lanka, this study is expected to contribute significantly to the development of this field in Sri Lanka.

The study begins with the existing theories in behavioral finance, based on which, hypotheses are proposed. Then, these hypotheses are tested through the questionnaires distributed to high networth individual investors at the Colombo Stock Exchange. The collected data are analyzed by using SPSS Software.

The result shows that there are four behavioral factors affecting the decision making of High Networth Investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors. Most of these factors have moderate impacts whereas Market factor has high influence.

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CHAPTER 1 – INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of the study

Stock market is a market where stocks are bought and sold in an economy, besides playing the role of a source for financing investment, stock market also performs a function as a signaling mechanism to managers regarding investment decisions, and a catalyst for corporate governance. However, stock market is best known for being the most effective channel for company's capital raise. People are interested in stock because of "long-term growth of capital, dividends, and a hedge against the inflationary erosion of purchasing power, the other feature that makes the stock market more attractive than other types of investment is its liquidity. Most people invest in stocks because they want to be the owners of the firm, from which they benefit when the company pay dividends or when stock price increases. However, many people buy stocks for the purpose of control over the firms. Regularly, shareholders need to own specific amount of shares to be in the board of directors who can make strategic decisions and set directions for the firms.

Tracing back to the past, financial activities relating to stock market seemed to exist in ancient civilization. The Roman became the pioneer in establishing corporative organizations, of which capital was raised by selling shares into the public, for bidding government contracts in the second century. The place for trading in Rome was near the Temple of Castor, which was called Forum. The Forum was said to be regarded as an immense stock exchange where people bought and sold not only shares, bonds but also various goods for cash, although some share-holding firms were held in Europe resembling old Roman companies, sole proprietorship was preferred by the fifteenth century, the first brokers appeared. During this period, Rialto Bridge of Venice was the business center for Europe. The commercial revolution during the sixteenth, seventeenth and eighteenth century was the impetus for the boom and bust in hundreds of joint-stock ventures. The first active market was held in Antwerp and then in Amsterdam in the sixteenth century, which was the financial center of northern Europe. Nowadays, the stock markets are classified into three types: developed, emerging and frontier according to the quality of markets criteria.

It is possible to consider stock market as the yardstick for economic strength and development. Thus, the movement of stock market trend represents the economic health of an

economy. The rise in share price tends to be associated with the increase in investment, which leads to the higher growth rate of a company in specific and an economy in general. Stock market affects economy through its liquidity. It is believed that firms may require long-term capital while investors do not intend to lose or relinquish control over their savings for such a long time. Liquidity allows investors to trade stocks easily and quickly while firms still have permanent use of capital for stable development. Furthermore, through risk diversification, stock market may influence economic growth by shifting investments into higher-return projects. Besides, stock market promotes the acquisition of firms' information, from which investors may benefit before the information is spread widely and prices change. Thus, investors are supposed to research and monitor firms closely. Additionally, stock market may push the development of an economy through efficient allocation of resources and better utilization of resources. Through stock market, savings flow from investors to the production of goods and services. Moreover, stock market helps agents to rearrange their portfolios quickly. Therefore, the importance and influence of stock market on the development of an economy cannot be denied.

The Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) was established under the Companies Act No.17 of 1982 and functions under license from the Securities and Exchange Commission of Sri Lanka (SEC). Since the end of Sri Lanka's three-decade civil war in 2009, the country has been on a fast track to achieving growth unmatched by most economies. Sri Lanka is poised to pull off average GDP growth of 8% per annum over the next three years, buoyed by sound fiscal and monetary policies, unprecedented growth in infrastructure development, evolution as a tourism and transshipment hub, and a rapidly growing middle class. Sri Lanka's medium-term GDP growth forecasts rank it as South Asia's fastest-growing economy.

The Colombo Stock Exchange (CSE) trades at a discount and offers attractive returns, underlined by strong corporate earnings potential. The CSE's low correlation to developed markets compared to most other emerging markets provides a unique diversification opportunity to investors seeking emerging market exposure. Furthermore, the CSE, together with the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) of Sri Lanka, is taking concrete measures to increase free float and market depth in order to improve investibility.

Given Sri Lanka's robust growth and the CSE's attractive returns, the Sri Lankan equity and debt markets offer a unique opportunity to investors in an investment era impacted by economic growth worries.

CSE has had a bull run unmatched by most other markets since 2009. As on 31 December 2013, the CSE had listed on it 289 companies covering 20 sectors, with a market capitalization of approximately USD19bn. The CSE witnessed remarkable growth after the end of the war, with the benchmark All Share Index (CSEALL) peaking at 7,800 points in February 2011. Given the bourse’s unprecedented growth levels, Bloomberg named it one of the best-performing stock markets in the world for the years 2009 and 2010. The CSEALL, on average, performed better (over June 2009-December 2013) than global indices (Exhibit 23) and some of the best-performing regional indices (Exhibit 24), although growth over the immediate post war period eased after mid-2011 due to a market correction. Positive market sentiment and conducive regulatory environment has driven market recovery since mid-2012. However, market fundamentals remain strong, with corporates performing well in the wake of the booming economy. The market grew 22% by end-2013 after it bottomed out in May 2012; improved market sentiments and the easing of market liquidity drove this growth.

Figure 1.1 CSE from 2010 -2015(Source: Bloomberg)

1.2.Problem Statement

Due to the positive correlation between stock market and economy, the rise of stock market will positively affect the development of the economy and vice versa. Thus, the decisions of investors on stock market play an important role in defining the market trend, which then influences the economy. To understand and give some suitable explanation for the investors' decisions, it is important to explore which behavioral factors affect the decisions of high net worth individual investors at the Colombo Stock Exchange and how these factors impact their investment performance. It will be useful for investors to understand common behaviors, from which justify their reactions for better returns. Security organizations may also use this information for better understanding about investors to forecast more accurately and give better recommendations. Thus, stock price will reflect its true value and the confidence levels of the high net worth investors will increase and more growth and stability can be experience at the Colombo Stock Exchange in the future.

When the Colombo Stock Exchange is compared with other exchanges in the world it is very clear and visible that it is a very volatile market and a small market in terms of number of instruments or companies listed and daily turnover. Thus the market is very unpredictable and could move either way up or down in big way, for an example during the two thousand and fifteen presidential elections the market moved upwards by four hundred points then retracted six hundred points and bounced back by four hundred points. This volatility can cause a lot chaos in the market where investors could be confused at the latter. Especially high networkth investors would be cautious when markets move in this manner. Therefore understanding the behavioral factors of the investors will benefit the stockbrokers to advice and trade in manner to satisfy the investors.

Figure 1.2 CSE before and after 2015 Presidential Elections (Source: Bloomberg)

1.3. Research Question

1. What are the behavioral factors that affect the decision making of the high network individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange?
2. What is the main factor that affects the decision making of the high network investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange?

1.4. Research Objectives

1. Identify the behavioral variables affecting the High Net worth Individual investors in their decision making in the Colombo Stock Exchange.
2. Identify the main behavioral variable that affect the High Net worth individuals' decisions making in the Colombo Stock exchange.
3. To make recommendations for any other research in the future for a similar topic in the same industry or even for a different exchange.

1.5. Significance of the study

Sri Lanka is an emerging economy in Asia with different ethnicity and many cultural characteristics similar to other Asian countries. This research will provide an overview of high net worth individual investors' decision making in the basis of behavioral finance at the Colombo Stock Exchange.

In 2012, Sri Lankan economy recorded an impressive growth of 7.2 per cent. It shows burgeoning growth after ended 30 years lasting civil war in May 2009 and moves to a higher sustainable growth path. All key sectors of the economy demonstrated a commendable performance in 2012, underpinned by the peaceful domestic environment, improved investor confidence, favorable macroeconomic conditions, and gradual recovery of the global economy from one of the deepest recessions in history. Sole proprietorship, partnership, companies and small business have been directly and indirectly contributing to economic growth and its sustainability. In boosting economic condition, all the business entities will flourish. Sri Lankan past 30 years war has seriously affected three generations of this country. Anyone can find ample of examples all over the country and many are still suffering from the loss of lives, limbs and material due to the war, no matter what race or religion they belonged to. Terrorism had been the major cause that hindered Sri Lanka achieving its development goals. However the government has allocated billions of rupees to develop the once war-torn north and east in par with the development taking place in the rest of the country. Improved economic performance, GDP growth, peace, and stability in Sri Lanka has led the IMF to change Sri Lanka's status from "Poverty Reduction and Growth Trust" to "Middle Income Emerging Market," an important landmark as the island nation makes its way down the path of development and reaps the benefits of peace. The improvement in status is expected to further open up international capital markets for the country and bring attention from investors targeting emerging markets with strong projected growth.

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Sri Lanka has reached a peak of USD 1.07 billion by December 2011, and the government expects it to rise to USD 1.75 in the year 2012. Sri Lanka is recognized as the most liberalized economy in South Asia, foreign investment is a crucial element representing Sri Lankan economic growth. The reasons behind for increasing capital investment are underpinned by peaceful domestic environment, improved investor

confidence, favorable macroeconomic conditions, and increased capacity utilization together with expansion of economic activity.

Therefore, nowadays, investment decisions play a vital role than ever before. Thus, this research has been designed to investigate the influence of behavioral factors in investment decisions and performance as emerging market in Sri Lanka. Main purpose of the study is in post war situation, how high net worth individual investors behave in the market and how that affects their decision making at the Colombo Stock exchange. Also this nature of study has not been attempted in Sri Lanka and thus there is a knowledge gap to be filled as behavioral finance is new to this industry and could help the security companies to identify and understand the investors and advise in that manner.

1.6. Limitation of the Study

The research is limited to and focuses only on the behaviors of high net worth individual investors at the Colombo Stock Exchange. It is necessary to have further research for all the investors' in the Colombo Stock Exchange in order to have a total picture of stock market in Sri Lanka. The main reason for limiting to the high net worth investor is because there is a lot of potential for the number of investors in the category to enter the stock market. Thus by identifying their behavioral patterns it would be easy to understand how to increase the number of high net worth individual investors at the Colombo Stock Exchange in the future.

CHAPTER 2 – CRITICAL REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1.Introduction

When using the labels "conventional" or "modern" to describe finance, it is the type of finance that is based on rational and logical theories, such as the capital asset pricing model (CAPM) and the efficient market hypothesis (EMH). These theories assume that people, for the most part, behave rationally and predictably.

For a while, theoretical and empirical evidence suggested that CAPM, EMH and other rational financial theories did a respectable job of predicting and explaining certain events. However, as time went on, academics in both finance and economics started to find anomalies and behaviors that couldn't be explained by theories available at the time. While these theories could explain certain "idealized" events, the real world proved to be a very messy place in which market participants often behaved very unpredictably.

One of the most rudimentary assumptions that conventional economics and finance makes is that people are rational "wealth maximizers" who seek to increase their own well-being. According to conventional economics, emotions and other extraneous factors do not influence people when it comes to making economic choices.

In most cases, however, this assumption doesn't reflect how people behave in the real world. The fact is people frequently behave irrationally. Consider how many people purchase lottery tickets in the hope of hitting the big jackpot. From a purely logical standpoint, it does not make sense to buy a lottery ticket when the odds of winning are overwhelming against the ticket holder. Despite this, millions of people spend countless dollars on this activity. These anomalies prompted academics to look to cognitive psychology to account for the irrational and illogical behaviors that modern finance had failed to explain. Behavioral finance seeks to explain our actions, whereas modern finance seeks to explain the actions of the "economic man".

The Colombo Stock Exchange is a very small market compared to other exchanges or market even when compared with the regional exchanges with only two hundred and ninety companies are listed and only company shares trade where as in other market you experience other instruments like Futures and Options, also a very important factor in liquidity where

investors are able to trade “buy or sell” at any given point with any quantity. This is also the main reason why the Colombo Stock Exchange is very volatile and unpredictable; this tends to motivate investors trades heavily and with greed try to get the highest price possible while booking profits. Eventually investors tend to forget the actual valuation of the company and move out of being an economic man. High networth individual investors contribute a lot to the market movements and thus identifying the main factors that affect their decision making in the Colombo Stock Exchange is vital, thus this research is identifying these factors and critical review of literature of these behavioral factors are mainly discussed in this chapter.

2.2.Important Contributors to behavioral finance

Like every other branch of finance, the field of behavioral finance has certain people that have provided major theoretical and empirical contributions. The following section provides a brief introduction to three of the biggest names associated with the field.

Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky

Cognitive psychologists Daniel Kahneman and Amos Tversky are considered the fathers of behavioral economics/finance. Since their initial collaborations in the late 1960s, this duo has published about 200 works, most of which relate to psychological concepts with implications for behavioral finance. In 2002, Kahneman received the Nobel Memorial Prize in Economic Sciences for his contributions to the study of rationality in economics.

Kahneman and Tversky have focused much of their research on the cognitive biases and heuristics that cause people to engage in unanticipated irrational behavior. Their most popular and notable works include writings about prospect theory and loss aversion.

Richard Thaler

While Kahneman and Tversky provided the early psychological theories that would be the foundation for behavioral finance, this field would not have evolved if it weren't for economist Richard Thaler.

During his studies, Thaler became more and more aware of the shortcomings in conventional

economic theories as they relate to people's behaviors. After reading a draft version of Kahneman and Tversky's work on prospect theory, Thaler realized that, unlike conventional economic theory, psychological theory could account for the irrationality in behaviors.

Thaler went on to collaborate with Kahneman and Tversky, blending economics and finance with psychology to present concepts, such as mental accounting, the endowment effect and other biases.

2.3.Critics for Behavioral Finance

Although behavioral finance has been gaining support in recent years, it is not without its critics. Some supporters of the efficient market hypothesis, for example, are vocal critics of behavioral finance.

The efficient market hypothesis is considered one of the foundations of modern financial theory. However, the hypothesis does not account for irrationality because it assumes that the market price of a security reflects the impact of all relevant information as it is released.

The most notable critic of behavioral finance is Eugene Fama, the founder of market efficiency theory. Professor Fama suggests that even though there are some anomalies that cannot be explained by modern financial theory, market efficiency should not be totally abandoned in favor of behavioral finance.

In fact, he notes that many of the anomalies found in conventional theories could be considered shorter-term chance events that are eventually corrected over time. In his 1998 paper, entitled "Market Efficiency, Long-Term Returns and Behavioral Finance", Fama argues that many of the findings in behavioral finance appear to contradict each other, and that all in all, behavioral finance itself appears to be a collection of anomalies that can be explained by market efficiency.

Some quotes by authors and websites that give an insight to behavioral finance is given below,

Behavioural finance is the study of the influence of psychology on the behaviour of financial practitioners and the subsequent effect on markets. Sewell (2005)

'I think of behavioral finance as simply "open-minded finance".'
Thaler (1993)

'This area of enquiry is sometimes referred to as "behavioral finance," but we call it "behavioral economics." Behavioral economics combines the twin disciplines of psychology and economics to explain why and how people make seemingly irrational or illogical decisions when they spend, invest, save, and borrow money.'
Belsky and Gilovich (1999)

'This paper examines the case for major changes in the behavioral assumptions underlying economic models, based on apparent anomalies in financial economics. Arguments for such changes based on claims of "excess volatility" in stock prices appear flawed for two main reasons: there are serious questions whether the phenomenon exists in the first place and, even if it did exist, whether radical change in behavioral assumptions is the best avenue for current research. The paper also examines other apparent anomalies and suggests conditions under which such behavioral changes are more or less likely to be adopted.'
Kleidon (1986)

'For most economists it is an article of faith that financial markets reach rational aggregate outcomes, despite the irrational behavior of some participants, since sophisticated players stand ready to capitalize on the mistakes of the naive. (This process, which we call poaching, includes but is not limited to arbitrage.) Yet financial markets have been subject to speculative fads, from Dutch tulip mania to junk bonds, and to occasional dramatic losses in value, such as occurred in October 1987, that are hard to interpret as rational. Descriptive decision theory, especially psychology (see D. Kahneman et al., 1982), can help to explain such aberrant macrophenomena. Here we propose some behavioral explanations of overall market outcomes—specifically of financial flows, that are of considerable practical consequence to both policymakers and finance practitioners.'
Patel, Zeckhauser and Hendricks (1991)

'Because psychology systematically explores human judgment, behavior, and well-being, it can teach us important facts about how humans differ from traditional economic assumptions. In this essay I discuss a selection of psychological findings relevant to economics. Standard economics assumes that each person has stable, well-defined preferences, and that she rationally maximizes those preferences. Section 2 considers what psychological research teaches us about the true form of preferences, allowing us to make economics more realistic within the rational choice framework. Section 3 reviews research on biases in judgment under uncertainty; because those biases lead people to make systematic errors in their attempts to maximize their preferences, this research poses a more radical challenge to the economics model. The array of psychological findings reviewed in Section 4 points to an even more radical critique of the economics model: Even if we are willing to modify our familiar assumptions about preferences, or allow that

people make systematic errors in their attempts to maximize those preferences, it is sometimes misleading to conceptualize people as attempting to maximize well-defined, coherent, or stable preferences.'
Rabin (1996)

'Market efficiency survives the challenge from the literature on long-term return anomalies. Consistent with the market efficiency hypothesis that the anomalies are chance results, apparent overreaction to information is about as common as underreaction, and post-event continuation of pre-event abnormal returns is about as frequent as post-event reversal. Most important, consistent with the market efficiency prediction that apparent anomalies can be due to methodology, most long-term return anomalies tend to disappear with reasonable changes in technique.'
Fama (1998)

'Recent literature in empirical finance is surveyed in its relation to underlying behavioral principles, principles which come primarily from psychology, sociology and anthropology. The behavioral principles discussed are: prospect theory, regret and cognitive dissonance, anchoring, mental compartments, overconfidence, over- and underreaction, representativeness heuristic, the disjunction effect, gambling behavior and speculation, perceived irrelevance of history, magical thinking, quasimagical thinking, attention anomalies, the availability heuristic, culture and social contagion, and global culture.'
Shiller (1998)

'The field of modern financial economics assumes that people behave with extreme rationality, but they do not. Furthermore, people's deviations from rationality are often systematic. Behavioral finance relaxes the traditional assumptions of financial economics by incorporating these observable, systematic, and very human departures from rationality into standard models of financial markets. We highlight two common mistakes investors make: excessive trading and the tendency to disproportionately hold on to losing investments while selling winners. We argue that these systematic biases have their origins in human psychology. The tendency for human beings to be overconfident causes the first bias in investors, and the human desire to avoid regret prompts the second.'
Barber and Odean (1999)

'Behavioral Economics is the combination of psychology and economics that investigates what happens in markets in which some of the agents display human limitations and complications. We begin with a preliminary question about relevance. Does some combination of market forces, learning and evolution render these human qualities irrelevant? No. Because of limits of arbitrage less than perfect agents survive and influence market outcomes. We then discuss three important ways in which humans deviate from the standard economic model. Bounded rationality reflects the limited cognitive abilities that constrain human problem solving. Bounded willpower captures the fact that people sometimes make choices that are not in their long-run interest. Bounded self-interest incorporates the comforting fact that humans are often willing to sacrifice their own interests to help others. We then illustrate how these concepts can be applied in two settings: finance and savings. Financial markets have greater arbitrage opportunities than other markets, so behavioral factors might be thought to be less important here, but we show that even here the limits of arbitrage create anomalies that the psychology of decision making helps explain. Since saving for retirement requires both complex calculations and willpower, behavioral factors are essential elements of any complete

descriptive theory.
Mullainathan and Thaler (2000)

'Behavioral finance is a rapidly growing area that deals with the influence of psychology on the behavior of financial practitioners.'
Shefrin (2000)

'Behavioral finance is the application of psychology to financial behavior—the behavior of practitioners.'
Shefrin (2000)

'Behavioral finance is the study of how psychology affects financial decision making and financial markets.'
Shefrin (2001)

'Behavioral finance argues that some financial phenomena can plausibly be understood using models in which some agents are not fully rational. The field has two building blocks: limits to arbitrage, which argues that it can be difficult for rational traders to undo the dislocations caused by less rational traders; and psychology, which catalogues the kinds of deviations from full rationality we might expect to see. We discuss these two topics, and then present a number of behavioral finance applications: to the aggregate stock market, to the cross-section of average returns, to individual trading behavior, and to corporate finance. We close by assessing progress in the field and speculating about its future course.'
Barberis and Thaler (2001)

'This essay provides a perspective on the trend towards integrating psychology into economics. Some topics are discussed, and arguments are provided for why movement towards greater psychological realism in economics will improve mainstream economics.'
Rabin (2001)

'The basic paradigm of asset pricing is in vibrant flux. The purely rational approach is being subsumed by a broader approach based upon the psychology of investors. In this approach, security expected returns are determined by both risk and misvaluation. This survey sketches a framework for understanding decision biases, evaluates the a priori arguments and the capital market evidence bearing on the importance of investor psychology for security prices, and reviews recent models.'
Hirshleifer (2001)

'Behavioral finance and behavioral economics are closely related fields which apply scientific research on human and social cognitive and emotional biases to better understand economic decisions and how they affect market prices, returns and the allocation of resources.'
Wikipedia (2005)

2.4.The impact behavioral finance has on Asian markets

Asia people seem to suffer from cognitive biases more than Western people do and Asian individual investors are considered as mere gamblers (Kim & Nofsinger, 2008, p.2). Theoretically, social scientists and psychologists believe that tendencies toward behavioral biases can be nurtured by culture although the levels may vary (Yates, Lee & Bush, 1997, p.87). Kim and Nofsinger (2008, p.2-5) explains the differences among cultures through an individualism collectivism continuum. Asian cultures are supposed to belong to socially collective paradigm, which has been argued for causing investors' overconfident resulting in behavioral bias. Cultural difference, more specifically, life experiences and education can affect behaviors, thus, it is believed that behavioral inclinations can differ among different cultures. Some evidences have been found to prove that Asian people exhibit more behavioral biases than people raised in Western countries or the United States (Yates et al., 1997, p.87). Although there are some literature about the behavioral biases difference between Asian people and Western people, the literature is still sparse (Kim & Nofsinger, 2008, p.3). According to Weber and Hsee (2000, p.34), "the bottom line is that the topic of culture and decision making has not received much attention from either decision researchers or cross cultural psychologists". In addition, a systematic literature about behaviors of Asian people and their effects on investment decision making is provided by Chen, Kim, Nofsinger and Rui (2007, p.425-451). In support of this theory, they find that Chinese investors suffer from an overconfidence bias and disposition effect more than U.S investors do (Kim & Nofsinger, 2008, p.3).

In the Colombo Stock Exchange investors mostly trade on credit and having the thought of that money not being owned by them they tend to trade more and try their best make money with it. The main and long followed and proved study is "Time Value For Money", which explains the money you own today will lose its value after a period of time. This mentality is always on the top of every investors mind and therefore heavy trades are always looking for opportunities to day trade and make money instantly. Nevertheless it may sound a promising method to follow but it also to be understood that day trading is with high risk and if the market moves the opposite way from what the investor expects he could lose more than what he expects. The high networth investors being the main contributors to the Colombo Stock Exchange as mentioned above security companies or brokering firms tend give more

importance to them and thus by identifying the main factors that affect their decision making will give an insight to what factors the majority of the market is affected by.

The main four factors that have been looked upon in this chapter by integrating modern finance with behavioral finance are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors. The four factors are explained below with studies done by others along with their sub factors which will be used to identify if these factors have impacts on the decision making of high networth individual investors and within these four factors and their sub factors which will impact the most on the same.

2.5.Heuristic Theory

Heuristics are defined as the rules of thumb, which makes decision making easier, especially in complex and uncertain environments (Ritter, 2003, p.431) by reducing the complexity of assessing probabilities and predicting values to simpler judgments (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974, p.1124). In general, these heuristics are quite useful, particularly when time is limited (Waweru et al., 2008, p.27), but sometimes they lead to biases (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974, p.1124; Ritter, 2003, p.431). Kahneman and Tversky seem to be ones of the first writers studying the factors belonging to heuristics when introducing three factors namely representativeness, availability bias, and anchoring (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974, p.1124-1131). Waweru et al. also list two factors named Gambler's fallacy and Overconfidence into heuristic theory (Waweru et al., 2008, p.27).

Representativeness refers to the degree of similarity that an event has with its parent population (DeBondt & Thaler, 1995, p.390) or the degree to which an event resembles its population (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974, p.1124). Representativeness may result in some biases such as people put too much weight on recent experience and ignore the average long-term rate (Ritter, 2003, p.432). A typical example for this bias is that investors often infer a company's high long-term growth rate after some quarters of increasing (Waweru et al., 2008, p.27). Representativeness also leads to the so-called "sample size neglect" which occurs when people try to infer from too few samples (Barberis & Thaler, 2003, p.1065). In stock market, when investors seek to buy "hot" stocks instead of poorly performed ones, this means that representativeness is applied. This behavior is an explanation for investor overreaction (DeBondt and Thaler, 1995, p.390).

The belief that a small sample can resemble the parent population from which it is drawn is known as the “law of small numbers” (Rabin, 2002, p.775; Statman, 1999, p.20) which may lead to a Gamblers’ fallacy (Barberis & Thaler, 2003, p.1065). More specifically, in stock market, Gamblers’ fallacy arises when people predict inaccurately the reverse points which are considered as the end of good (or poor) market returns (Waweru et al., 2008,p.27). In addition, when people subject to status quo bias, they tend to select suboptimal alternative simply because it was chosen previously (Kempf and Ruenzi, 2006, p.204).

Anchoring is a phenomena used in the situation when people use some initial values to make estimation, which are biased toward the initial ones as different starting points yield different estimates (Kahneman & Tversky, 1974, p.1128). In financial market, anchoring arises when a value scale is fixed by recent observations. Investors always refer to the initial purchase price when selling or analyzing. Thus, today prices are often determined by those of the past. Anchoring makes investors to define a range for a share price or company’s income based on the historical trends, resulting in under-reaction to unexpected changes. Anchoring has some connection with representativeness as it also reflects that people often focus on recent experience and tend to be more optimistic when the market rises and more pessimistic when the market falls (Waweru et al., 2008, p.28).

When people overestimate the reliability of their knowledge and skills, it is the manifestation of overconfidence (DeBondt & Thaler, 1995, p.389, Hvide, 2002, p.15). Many studies show that excessive trading is one effect of investors. There is evidence showing that financial analysts revise their assessment of a company slowly, even in case there is a strong indication proving that assessment is no longer correct. Investors and analysts are often overconfident in areas that they have knowledge (Evans, 2006, p.20). Overconfidence is believed to improve persistence and determination, mental facility, and risk tolerance. In other words, overconfidence can help to promote professional performance. It is also noted that overconfidence can enhance other’s perception of one’s abilities, which may help to achieve faster promotion and greater investment duration (Oberlechner & Osler, 2004, p.3).

Availability bias happens when people make use of easily available information excessively. In stock trading area, this bias manifest itself through the preference of investing in local companies which investors are familiar with or easily obtain information, despite the

fundamental principles so-called diversification of portfolio management for optimization (Waweru et al., 2003, p.28).

2.6. Prospect Theory

Expected Utility Theory (EUT) and prospect theory are considered as two approaches to decision-making from different perspectives. Prospect theory focuses on subjective decision-making influenced by the investors' value system, whereas EUT concentrates on investors' rational expectations (Filbeck, Hatfield & Horvath, 2005, p.170-171). EUT is the normative model of rational choice and descriptive model of economic behavior, which dominates the analysis of decision making under risk. Nonetheless, this theory is criticized for failing to explain why people are attracted to both insurance and gambling. People tend to under-weigh probable outcomes compared with certain ones and people response differently to the similar situations depending on the context of losses or gains in which they are presented (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979, p.263). Prospect theory describes some states of mind affecting an individual's decision-making processes including Regret aversion, Loss aversion and Mental accounting (Waweru et al., 2003, p.28).

Regret is an emotion occurs after people make mistakes. Investors avoid regret by refusing to sell decreasing shares and willing to sell increasing ones. Moreover, investors tend to be more regretful about holding losing stocks too long than selling winning ones too soon (Forgel & Berry, 2006, p.107; Lehenkari & Perttunen, 2004, p.116).

Loss aversion refers to the difference level of mental penalty people have from a similar size loss or gain (Barberis & Huang, 2001, p.1248). There is evidence showing that people are more distressed at the prospect of losses than they are pleased by equivalent gains (Barberis & Thaler, 2003, p.1077). Moreover, a loss coming after prior gain is proved less painful than usual while a loss arriving after a loss seems to be more painful than usual (Barberis & Huang, 2001, p.1248). In addition, Lehenkari and Perttunen (2004, p.116) find that both positive and negative returns in the past can boost the negative relationship between the selling trend and capital losses of investors, suggesting that investors are loss averse. Risk aversion can be understood as a common behavior of investor, nevertheless it may result in bad decision affecting investor's wealth (Odean, 1998a, p.1899).

Mental accounting is a term referring to “the process by which people think about and evaluate their financial transactions” (Barberis & Huang, 2001, p.1248). Mental accounting allows investors to organize their portfolio into separate accounts (Barberis & Thaler, 2003, p.1108; Ritter, 2003, p.431). From own empirical study, Rockenbach (2004, p.524) suggests that connection between different investment possibilities is often not made as it is useful for arbitrage free pricing.

2.7. Market Theory

DeBondt and Thaler (1995, p.396) state that financial markets can be affected by investors’ behaviors in the way of behavioral finance. If the perspectives of behavioral finance are correct, it is believed that the investors may have over- or under-reaction to price changes or news; extrapolation of past trends into the future; a lack of attention to fundamentals underlying a stock; the focus on popular stocks and seasonal price cycles. These market factors, in turns, influence the decision making of investors in the stock market. Waweru et al. (2008, p.36) identifies the factors of market that have impact on investors’ decision making: Price changes, market information, past trends of stocks, customer preference, over-reaction to price changes, and fundamentals of underlying stocks.

Normally, changes in market information, fundamentals of the underlying stock and stock price can cause over/under-reaction to the price change. These changes are empirically proved to have the high influence on decision-making behavior of investors. Researchers convince that over-reaction (DeBondt & Thaler, 1985, p.804) or under-reaction (Lai, 2001, p.215) to news may result in different trading strategies by investors and hence influence their investment decisions. Waweru et al. (2008, p.36) conclude that market information has very high impact on making decision of investors and this makes the investors, in some way, tend to focus on popular stocks and other attention-grabbing events that are relied on the stock market information. Moreover, Barber and Odean (2000, p.800) emphasize that investors are impacted by events in the stock market which grab their attention, even when they do not know if these events can result good future investment performance. Odean (1998a, p.1887) explores that many investors trade too much due to their overconfidence. These investors totally rely on the information quality of the market or stocks that they have when making decisions of investment.

Waweru et al. (2008, p.37) indicate that price change of stocks has impact on their investment behavior at some level. Odean (1999, p.1292) states that investors prefer buying to selling stocks that experience higher price changes during the past two years. Change in stock price in this context can be considered as an attention-grabbing occurrence in the market by investors. Additionally, Caparrelli et al. (2004, p.223) propose that investors are impacted by herding effect and tend to move in the same flow with the others when price changes happen. Besides, investors may revise incorrectly estimates of stock returns to deal with the price changes so that this affects their investment decision-making (Waweru et al.,2008, p.37).

Many investors tend to focus on popular stocks or hot stocks in the market (Waweru et al., 2008, p.37). Odean (1999, p.1296) proposes that investors usually choose the stocks that attract their attention. Besides, the stock selection also depends on the investors' preferences. Momentum investors may prefer stocks that have good recent performance while rational investors tend to sell the past losers and this may help them to postpone taxes. In contrast, behavioral investors prefer selling their past winners to postpone the regret related to a loss that they can meet for their stock trading decisions (Waweru et al.2008, p.30). Besides, past trends of stocks are also explored to impact the decision making behavior of the investors at a certain level by Waweru et al. (2008, p.37). In this concept, investors usually analyze the past trends of stocks by technical analysis methods before deciding an investment.

2.8.Herding Factor

Herding effect in financial market is identified as tendency of investors' behaviors to follow the others' actions. Practitioners usually consider carefully the existence of herding, due to the fact that investors rely on collective information more than private information can result the price deviation of the securities from fundamental value; therefore, many good chances for investment at the present can be impacted. Academic researchers also pay their attention to herding; because its impacts on stock price changes can influence the attributes of risk and return models and this has impacts on the viewpoints of asset pricing theories (Tan, Chiang, Mason & Nelling, 2008, p.61).

In the perspective of behavior, herding can cause some emotional biases, including conformity, congruity and cognitive conflict, the home bias and gossip. Investors may prefer herding if they believe that herding can help them to extract useful and reliable information. Whereas, the performances of financial professionals, for example, fund managers, or

financial analysts, are usually evaluated by subjectively periodic assessment on a relative base and the comparison to their peers. In this case, herding can contribute to the evaluation of professional performance because low-ability ones may mimic the behavior of their high-ability peers in order to develop their professional reputation (Kallinterakis, Munir & Markovic, 2010, p.306).

In the security market, herding investors base their investment decisions on the masses' decisions of buying or selling stocks. In contrast, informed and rational investors usually ignore following the flow of masses, and this makes the market efficient. Herding, in the opposite, causes a state of inefficient market, which is usually recognized by speculative bubbles. In general, herding investors act the same ways as prehistoric men who had a little knowledge and information of the surrounding environment and gathered in groups to support each other and get safety (Caparrelli et al., 2004, p.223). There are several elements that impact the herding behavior of an investor. The more confident the investors are, the more they rely on their private information for the investment decisions. In this case, investors seem to be less interested in herding behaviors. When the investors put a large amount of capital into their investment, they tend to follow the others' actions to reduce the risks, at least in the way they feel. Besides, the preference of herding also depends on types of investors, for example, individual investors have tendency to follow the crowds in making investment decision more than institutional investors (Goodfellow, Bohl & Gebka, 2009, p.213).

Waweru et al. (2008, p.31) propose that herding can drive stock trading and create the momentum for stock trading. However, the impact of herding can break down when it reaches a certain level because the cost to follow the herd may increase to get the increasing abnormal returns. Waweru et al. (2008, p.37) identify stock investment decisions that an investor can be impacted by the others: buying, selling, choice of stock, length of time to hold stock, and volume of stock to trade. Waweru et al. conclude that buying and selling decisions of an investor are significantly impacted by others' decisions, and herding behavior helps investors to have a sense of regret aversion for their decisions. For other decisions: choice of stock, length of time to hold stock, and volume of stock to trade, investors seem to be less impacted by herding behavior. However, these conclusions are given to the case of institutional investors; thus, the result can be different in the case of individual investors

because, as mentioned above, individuals tend to herd in their investment more than institutional investors.

2.9. Conclusion

The distinction between modern and new finance is more clear-cut than ever due to their different theoretical approaches --normative and positive. Behavioral finance takes its firm stance in the new finance school of thought by attacking the underlying assumptions of modern finance theory which follow the optimality principle and frictionless market and using the more mundane empirical observations and the experimental results of extensive studies in other social science disciplines such as psychology, sociology, and political science.

The Colombo Stock Exchange has had a significant growth after a thirty year war from two thousand and nine. The market mainly experienced before the end of the ethnic was a very small and expected the market movement on news and financial results. Then the industry was small and the number of security companies, investors and brokers were a handful where everyone knew each other and in terms of foreign participant was quite small compare to the market now. After the war and when investors not only in Sri Lanka but also from the others countries started to look in to and invest and eventually the market grew to a new high and investors' expectations were rocketed. Whilst understanding the growth of the market along with the industry with new investors local and foreign and the security companies along with new brokers one did not understand that predicting the market would be as easy as it was before two thousand and nine before the end of war. This had an impact on every stakeholder of the market as to the market could not be predicted in terms of the modern finance or in an economic way, and therefore technical analysis which works more on predictions on past trends and charts were look in to, but still there were instances where the market could not be predicted to the best possible point even by the most experienced or by an expert in the market.

Since the market always moves on how the majorities of the investors' feel and react to the situations mostly it is the high networth investors that always move the market as in terms of demand and supply. Even though the investment amount is lesser than funds in the market, who usually have a set of rules and invest only after certain approvals and mostly believe in fundamentals or in the modern finance will always sticks to a price and not step out of the

line. High networth investors always use their own money and could take their own decisions and make decision according to the situations and thus might have the opportunity to invest before other funds. Therefore it very important and vital to understand the factors that have an impact on the high networth investors' decision on the Colombo Stock Exchange and since the market is now somewhat matured and has been called a frontier market it is best to identify which behavioral finance theories explained above have an impact on them.

CHAPTER 3 – RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1.Introduction

This chapter explains about the research methodology in terms of research approaches, research strategies, research choice, research techniques and procedures for data collection and analysis.

It also explains about the conceptual model of the research along with its operationalization and development of hypothesis.

3.2.Operationalization

It is understood and identify through literature that there are four main variables in behavioral finance that effect decision making of investors in a stock market, regardless of exchange, region or company, which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding.

These four main factors have sub factors to identify the effect on each and how decisions are made in line with each of them. These sub factors will help to identify in this research on which basis the investors make decisions before investing and finally by which main factor their decisions are affected with.

The last two questions are to test the dependent variable which is Decision Making of High Network Investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

Factors	Sub – Factors	Questions
Heuristic	Representativeness Overconfidence Anchoring Gambler’s fallacy Ability bias	Questions 7 -13
Prospect	Loss aversion Regret aversion Mental accounting	Questions 14-19
Market	Price changes Market information Past trends of stocks Fundamentals of underlying stocks Customer preference Over reaction to price	Questions 20 -25

	changes	
Herding	Following other investors trading patterns	Questions 26 – 29
Decision Making	Satisfaction of decisions made	Questions 30 – 31

Table 3.1 Operationalization

Each sub factor mentioned above of every main factor has been explained in chapter 2 literature review. The explanation given in that chapter is used for developing the questionnaire to suit the research. Above mentioned questions are targeting each main factor by considering the sub factors effects on the respondent, therefore identifying the main factors effect on them as well.

3.3. Conceptual Framework of the research

Figure 3.1 Conceptual Model

HYPOTHESIS H1 0: HEURISTIC FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H1 1: HEURISTIC FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H2 0: PROSPECT FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H2 1: PROSPECT FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H3 0: MARKET FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H3 1: MARKET FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H4 0: HERDING FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

HYPOTHESIS H4 1: HERDING FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE

3.4. Research Design

Research design provides the framework for data collection and analysis. In order to understand the common behaviors of high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange, self-completed questionnaires are believed to be the best options with close ended questions and a Likert scale of six, where the answers will be limited to either positive or negative. The questionnaire will have at least minimum of three questions representing each main behavioral factors which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding theories.

3.5. Sample design

As the research aims at exploring the behavioral factors at the Colombo Stock Exchange, a relative large sample size is recommended. The sample size depends on researchers' available resources including time, finance and human.

“Snow Ball” sampling method is used for this research because identifying the population could be a difficult task as due to the trading patterns of high networth investors some could have liquidated their portfolios, and mostly these investors expect their security companies to keep their trading information secured and undisclosed to others. Therefore this method helps

the stockbrokers or the security company to decide on their choice to select the best group for this research or the top ranking high networth individuals in terms of turnover or brokerage.

The questionnaires are sent to the Colombo Stock Exchange to be sent to the top ten security companies in terms of turnover and market share which are members of the Colombo Stock Exchange. Then, these questionnaires are sent to brokers of these companies, who are responsible for completing by sending or filling the questionnaires by calling their best high networth individual investors of their choice. Although investors from these ten companies are not the whole population, they do account for above 50% of the whole population, which can be considered as representativeness to some extent. This issue can be considered as a limitation of this study.

3.6.Data collection methods and Techniques Used for Research Analysis

The questionnaire is divided into two parts, personal information and behavioral factors influencing investment decisions. In the part of personal information, nominal and ordinal measurements are used. Nominal scales are used to classify objects while ordinal scales are necessary for objectives, classifying and ranking order of objects or observations.

The questionnaire is based on the theories of behavioral factors influencing the decision making of the high networth investors in the stock market which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding. In these parts the six point Likert scales, which are rating scales widely used for asking respondents' opinions and attitudes, are utilized to ask the individual investors to evaluate the degrees of their agreement with the impacts of behavioral factors on their investment decision as well as the statements of investment performance. The six point in the scale are respectively from 1 to 6 extremely disagree, highly disagree, somewhat disagree, somewhat agree, highly agree and extremely agree. The six point Likert scale measurements are used in this research to limit the bias evaluation of respondents because the respondents cannot find the means of the six point scale in the questionnaire where they easily find in a five point scale or seven point scale. The collected data are processed and analyzed by the SPSS software. At first, the data are cleaned by removing the questionnaire with poor quality such as including too many missing values or bias ratings and then techniques are used for the data to achieve the research objectives.

CHAPTER 4 – DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1. Introduction

This chapter is to analysis the data collected by the SPSS software. First to check if the variables are reliable to continue the research and then after that test the hypothesis that were discussed and developed previously.

4.2. Data Analysis on Personal Information

The respondents for the questionnaires received were a total of hundred and four. The questionnaire used for this research has a total of twenty nine questions and the first six questions out of them are personal questions, below are the analysis on the personal questions that will clearly state the gender percentage and the age category along with other market related questions.

Below diagram (figure 4.1) shows the gender with age categories of the respondents, it is visible that the main respondents for this research are males and they are between thirty six and fifty six.

Figure 4.1 Age and Gender analysis (Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20)

The next diagram (figure 4.2) shows the breakdown of the investors and their highest education and the number of years they have been working in the corporate world.

Figure 4.2 Year of Working and Highest Qualification analysis (Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20)

This diagram (figure 4.3) concentrates on how many years the investor has been trading in the Colombo Stock Exchange and how much they have invested in total accumulative of the year's active in the market.

Figure 4.3 Year in Market and Total Invested analysis (Source: IBM SPSS Statistics 20)

4.3. Data analysis of the Independent Variables

Questions from seven to twenty nine are related to the independent variables to test the factors affecting the decision making of High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange and the questions from thirty to thirty one is related to the dependent variable, below analysis is a reliable analysis done to test the reliability of each independent variable and the questions related to the dependent variable.

Heuristic Theory (Questions 7 – 13)

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.677	7

Table 4.1 Heuristic Reliability Test

Prospect Theory (Questions 14- 19)

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.707	6

Table 4.2 Prospect Reliability Test

Market Theory (Questions 20-25)

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.644	6

Table 4.3 Market Reliability Test

Herding Theory (Questions 26-29)

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.935	4

Table 4.4 Herding Reliability Test

Decision Making (Questions 30-31)

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.679	2

Table 4.5 Decision Making Reliability Test

Since the reliability test confirms that all variables are above 0.6 Cronbach’s Alpha thus these factors and the questions are reliable enough to follow further analysis.

Impact levels of independent variables that have an impact on the High Networth Individual Investors decision making. The Impact levels of the above mentioned factors on the decision making of High Networth Individual investors are identified by calculating the mean value of each questions and thus calculating the average mean of each factors. The mean values of these factors can decide their impact levels on the decision making as the following rules:

- Mean values are less than 2 shows that the variables have very low impacts
- Mean values are from 2 to 3 shows that the variables have low impacts
- Mean values are from 3 to 4 shows that the variables have moderate impacts
- Mean values are from 4 to 5 shows that the variables have high impacts
- Mean values are more 5 shows that the variables have very high impacts

4.3.1. Impact Levels of the Heuristic Factor on decision making

Statistics

		Heuristic Q1	Heuristic Q2	Heuristic Q3	Heuristic Q4	Heuristic Q5	Heuristic Q6	Heuristic Q7
N	Valid	104	104	104	103	104	104	104
	Missing	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Mean		4.0962	4.1442	3.6346	4.1262	3.9135	3.2404	4.0769

Table 4.6 Heuristic Means

Above given is the mean of the Heuristic Factor to identify the impact levels of the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange. As per the rules given above by calculating the average mean of all the questions that represent the Heuristic Factor the impact levels can be identified.

Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean
Hueristic	104	3.8892
Valid N (listwise)	104	

Table 4.7 Heuristic Mean Average

Since the average mean is between 3 – 4 , as per to the rules the Heuristic Factor has a moderate level of impact in the decision making of the High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock exchange.

4.3.2. Impact Levels of the Prospect Factor on decision making

		Statistics					
		Prospect Q1	Prospect Q2	Prospect Q3	Prospect Q4	Prospect Q5	Prospect Q6
N	Valid	104	104	104	104	104	104
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.0192	3.9231	3.8654	4.0577	4.1442	3.3750

Table 4.8 Prospect Mean

Above given is the mean of the Prospect Factor to identify the impact levels of the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange. As per the rules given above by calculating the average mean of all the questions that represent the Prospect Factor the impact levels can be identified.

Descriptive Statistics		
	N	Mean
Prospect	104	3.8974
Valid N (listwise)	104	

Table 4.9 Prospect Mean Average

Since the average mean is between 3 – 4 , as per to the rules the Prospect Factor has a moderate level of impact in the decision making of the High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock exchange.

4.3.3. Impact Levels of the Market Factor on decision making

		Statistics					
		Market Q1	Market Q2	Market Q3	Market Q4	Market Q5	Market Q6
N	Valid	104	104	104	104	104	104
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		5.0962	4.2212	5.3269	4.9231	4.6058	5.4231

Table 4.10 Market Mean

Above given is the mean of the Market Factor to identify the impact levels of the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange. As per the

rules given above by calculating the average mean of all the questions that represent the Market Factor the impact levels can be identified.

	N	Mean
Market	104	4.9327
Valid N (listwise)	104	

Table 4.11 Market Mean Average

Since the average mean is between 4 – 5 , as per to the rules the Market Factor has a high level of impact in the decision making of the High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

4.3.4. Impact Levels of the Herding Factor on decision making

		Herding Q1	Herding Q2	Herding Q3	Herding Q4
N	Valid	104	104	104	104
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean		3.8173	3.9135	3.3558	3.1635

Table 4.12 Herding Mean

Above given is the mean of the Herding Factor to identify the impact levels of the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange. As per the rules given above by calculating the average mean of all the questions that represent the Herding Factor the impact levels can be identified.

	N	Mean
Herding	104	3.5625
Valid N (listwise)	104	

Table 4.13 Herding Mean Average

Since the average mean is between 3 - 4 , as per to the rules the Herding Factor has a moderate level of impact in the decision making of the High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

As per the above findings the four behavioral factors used in this research have been identified to have an impact on the decision making of the high networth individual investors and the level of impact is given below.

Factor	Mean Average	Level of Impact
Heuristic Factor	3.8903	Moderate
Prospect Factor	3.8974	Moderate
Market Factor	4.9327	High
Herding Factor	3.5625	Moderate

Table 4.14 Factor Mean Average and Level of Impact

The above tables states that all the four behavioral factors that have been discussed and used for this research which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors have an impact on the decision making of High Networth Individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

Also the factor that has the highest mean which is stated to have a high level of impact on the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange is proven to be the main factor that has an impact and that is the Market Factor.

4.4. Hypothesis Testing

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Hueristic	104	3.8892	.69491	.06814

Table 4.15 One Sample Statistics – Heuristic

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Hueristic	57.075	103	.000	3.88919	3.7541	4.0243

Table 4.16 One Sample Test – Heuristic

Above shows the hypothesis testing for the Hueristic Factor and since the mean is 3.8892 and the Sig. (2-tailed) is below .05 **HYPOTHESIS H1 0: HEURISTIC FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is rejected and **HYPOTHESIS H1 1: HEURISTIC FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF**

HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE is accepted.

		Decision	Hueristic
Decision	Pearson Correlation	1	.068
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	104	104
Hueristic	Pearson Correlation	.068	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	104	104

Table 4.17 Correlations – Heuristic

Above analysis of Pearson correlation shows that the relationship between the Heuristic factor and the Dependent variable is positive.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Prospect	104	3.8974	.66233	.06495

Table 4.18 One Sample Statistics - Prospect

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Prospect	60.010	103	.000	3.89744	3.7686	4.0262

Table 4.19 One Sample Test - Prospect

Above shows the hypothesis testing for the Prospect Factor and since the mean is 3.8974 and the Sig. (2-tailed) is below .05 **HYPOTHESIS H2 0: PROSPECT FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is rejected and **HYPOTHESIS H2 1: PROSPECT FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is accepted.

		Decision	Prospect
Decision	Pearson Correlation	1	.429
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	104	104
Prospect	Pearson Correlation	.429	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	104	104

Table 4.20 Correlations – Prospect

Above analysis of Pearson correlation shows that the relationship between the Prospect factor and the Dependent variable is positive.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Market	104	4.9327	.63794	.06256

Table 4.21 One Sample Statistics- Market

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Market	78.853	103	.000	4.93269	4.8086	5.0568

Table 4.22 One Sample Test - Market

Above shows the hypothesis testing for the Market Factor and since the mean is 4.9327 and the Sig. (2-tailed) is below .05 **HYPOTHESIS H3 0: MARKET FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is rejected and **HYPOTHESIS H3 1: MARKET FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is accepted.

		Decision	Market
Decision	Pearson Correlation	1	.292
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	104	104
Market	Pearson Correlation	.292	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	104	104

Table 4.23 Correlations – Market

Above analysis of Pearson correlation shows that the relationship between the Market factor and the Dependent variable is positive.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Herding	104	3.5625	1.11409	.10925

Table 4.24 One Sample Statistics - Herding

	Test Value = 0					
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Herding	32.610	103	.000	3.56250	3.3458	3.7792

Table 4.25 One Sample Test - Herding

Above shows the hypothesis testing for the Market Factor and since the mean is 3.5625 and the Sig. (2-tailed) is below .05 **HYPOTHESIS H4 0: HERDING FACTOR HAS NO IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is rejected and **HYPOTHESIS H4 1: HERDING FACTOR HAS AN IMPACT ON THE DECISION MAKING OF HIGH NETWORTH INDIVIDUAL INVESTORS IN THE COLOMBO STOCK EXCHANGE** is accepted.

Correlations		
	Decision	Herding
Pearson Correlation	1	.037
Decision Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
N	104	104
Pearson Correlation	.037	1
Herding Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
N	104	104

Table 4.26 Correlations – Herding

Above analysis of Pearson correlation shows that the relationship between the Herding factor and the Dependent variable is positive.

Chapter 5 – Conclusions and Recommendations

5.1. Summary of the study

The research is about identifying the behavioral factors that have an impact on the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange and from these factors identifying the main factor that has the highest level of impact. The four behavioral factors that were used in this research are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors.

The six point Likert Scale measurement was used for this research and the reliability was tested by Cronbach's Alpha, which proves that behavioral finance can be used in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

The findings in the study could benefit the High Networth Individual Investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange and also be used by the security companies and their stock brokers.

5.2. Conclusion of the study

The conclusion of the study given below after validating the hypothesis and fulfilling the objectives of the study,

Identify the behavioral variables affecting the High Net worth Individual investors in their decision making in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

The behavioral factors identified and tested upon in this study are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors. The testing of the hypothesis, all null values were rejected and thus all behavioral factors discussed have an impact on the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange.

Identify the main behavioral variable that affects the High Net Worth Individuals' decisions making in the Colombo Stock exchange.

After studying the four behavioral factors and testing the hypothesis and accepting, it was proven that the Market Factor has a higher significant impact on the decision making of the

high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange with the highest mean average of 4.9327.

5.3. Recommendations

As discussed before there are four behavioral factors that affect the decision making of the high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange, which are Heuristic, Prospect, Market and Herding factors and they have a positive impact on them with the Market factor having a higher impact.

Therefore I recommend security companies to target on these factors and mainly on Market factors when doing a research document or a recommendations document on any company or stock. Along with the modern finance integrating the behavioral factors also will be an advantage as for security companies as it will be a method to cover all aspects of the customer exceptions or rather the investors' view of analysis.

Stockbrokers or Investment Advisors, this study will be very useful and keeping in mind the main factors whilst speaking with an investor or advising them or recommending a stock or company it will be very easy to provide exactly what is needed by the high networth individual investors and therefore can directly pitch into their line of analysis.

5.4. Suggestions for further research

This study was done in a short period of time and thus data collection was not very easy as it was time consuming to receive the questionnaires from the respondent and thus the respondent was only of hundred and four. I would suggest that anyone that continues from this research should look to study a larger sample as then there would be a bit more accurate answer as to these factors.

As this is a the first time that a research of this sort has been attempted even though behavioral finance would have been used on the whole market this study only concentrates on high networth individual investors in the Colombo Stock Exchange. At time where our market is growing and is maturing on its own even though it is a slow process there is a lot of opportunity for researches in behavioral finance has it is proven and visible that these factors have an impact on it. These areas could be new to the market as before the only areas that were looked upon is fundamental or technical analysis, by integrating both with a clear

picture is will be easier for market intermediaries to take decision in terms of buying and selling.

Lastly I feel it is also important that the whole market is taken into consideration and not only individual investors but also the institutional and fund managers are included in a research study of this sort.

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APPENDIX 1 : QUESTIONNAIRE